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NanoBubbles project

D2.5 - Data Management Plan

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Project summary:

Science relies on the correction of errors to advance, yet in practice scientists find it difficult to erase erroneous and exaggerated claims from the scientific record. Recent discussion of a “replication crisis” has impaired trust in science both among scientists and non-scientists; yet we know little about how non-replicated or even fraudulent claims can be removed from the scientific record. This project combines approaches from the natural, engineering, and social sciences and the humanities (Science and Technology Studies) to understand how error correction in science works and what obstacles it faces, and stages events for scientists to reflect on error and overpromising.

The project’s focus is nanobiology, a highly interdisciplinary field founded around the year 2000 that has already seen multiple episodes of overpromising and promotion of erroneous claims. We examine three such “bubbles”: the claim that nanoparticles can cross the blood-brain barrier; that nanoparticles can penetrate the cell membrane; and the promotion of the “protein corona” concept to describe ordinary adsorption of proteins on nanoparticles. Findings based on error (non)correction in nanobiology should be generalizable to other new, highly interdisciplinary fields such as synthetic biology and artificial intelligence.

We trace claims and corrections in various channels of scientific communication (journals, social media, advertisements, conference programs, etc.) via innovative digital methods. We examine error (non)correction practices in scientific conferences via ethnographic participant-observation. We follow the history of conferences, journals, and other sites of error (non)correction from the 1970s (before nanobio per se existed) to the present. And we attempt to replicate neurobiological claims and, in case of non-replication, document obstacles to correcting those claims. Finally, we will spark a dialogue within the nanobiology community by organizing workshops and events at conferences for practitioners. Through the study and practice of nanobiology, we will analyse how, when and why science fails to correct itself, and explore ways to improve the reliability and efficiency of the scientific process.

Team members' institutions:

Université Sorbonne Paris Nord, Université Grenoble Alpes, Radboud University, Maastricht University, University of Twente, CNRS, IRIT, Ecole des Ponts ParisTech

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1. Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

For this first version of the DMP, the project members have identified the following research outputs to be considered as data:

- Recordings and transcripts of interviews
- Field notes
- Scientific literature
- Scholarly works metadata
- Digital ephemera
- Software codes
- Experimental data and protocols
- Physical objects

1.1. Recordings and transcripts of interviews

Ethnographic, historical and informal interviews will be made. The transcripts of the interviews are generated from recordings that were made with the interviewees. They come in three different formats: recording, raw transcript, and pseudonymized transcript. This pseudonymisation process means that personal data would no longer be able to be attributed to a specific person without the use of additional information kept separately.

The transcription is done manually or with a tool installed on laptops.

Recordings are mp4 files. Experience shows that about 50 interviews are conducted per project. This requires between 250 and 500MB of storage, for sound files of 80 min/50MB each.

1.2. Field notes

Observations and thoughts will result in raw and pseudonymized notes in text format (docx or txt files). Photos and screenshots will sometimes be taken; these could be large files that require more storage space.

Image files are storage consuming with an estimation of 800MB max per fieldwork per member, amounting to less than 3GB storage needed.

1.3. Scientific literature

- **Documents coming from structured databases**

We will build up corpora of scientific texts by querying several legal sources, via their APIs or by downloading.

These documents will mostly be journal articles, but will also include magazine and newspaper articles, monographs, edited volumes and conference proceedings, textbooks, policy documents, government reports, parliamentary testimony, patents, legislation...

We plan to query the Elsevier and PubMed databases, Open Access archives, the ISTE database (French national database of text archives) and the downloadable corpus of the PLoS journal.

In all cases (for example for the exploration of news archives of specific scientific journals), we will abide by the technical limitations set by these content providers (sometimes via

subscription-based services held by members' institutions). These mainly concern the volumes that can be downloaded simultaneously and the operating licences.

We also plan to explore existing corpora, which are not corpora of full-texts, but corpora already resulting from the mining of full-texts. These are notably corpora of citation contexts (more or less sentences) but also the one that a team member is building within another research project (Cita&Re¹), and which will be shared in open access.

- **Heterogeneous documents**

In some cases, the documents collected to be read or mined are collected from interviewees, or are derived from photographs taken during visits to archival centres.

These documents include technical reports, advertisements and promotional literature, conference programs, funding proposals and reviewers' comments, draft publications and reviewers'/editors' comments, correspondence, lab notebooks, manuals, conference reports, budgets...

We do not consider the scientific literature consulted/read for the scientific progress of the project as research data and it will be collected and shared between members via Zotero.

Wherever possible, the preferred format is XML based on the TEI schema, JSON as well.

In some cases, it will be necessary to convert PDF files into XML-TEI, and even OCRise images to get texts.

Finally, for the corpus of citation contexts, the CSV format is preferred.

The processing of the XML files can be done on the secured servers of the University of Grenoble-Alpes or at the IRIT (University of Toulouse). An estimate of the volumes resulting from this exploitation will be made once the delineation of the corpora has been decided by the team. PDF files and scans or photos of documents will result in large files, about 5/6GB seem necessary.

1.4. Scholarly works metadata

In this project, the metadata describing documents that will constitute the corpora of scientific documents are themselves research data that will be analysed and processed. These metadata are often even acquired before the constitution of corpora of full-texts with the querying of bibliographic databases (Scopus, Dimensions, PubMed, Ulrichsweb...), specific databases (abstracts of funded proposals, retractions information with Retraction Watch/CrossRef), or dedicated services (Elsevier ICSR lab).

They are very easily accessible. They include textual data (authors, title, abstract, keywords, affiliations, name of the journal, etc.), but also numerical data (dates, disciplinary field codes) and identifiers (DOIs, ISSN).

Depending on the use made of this metadata, it will be processed in XML format or in CSV. The underlying schema will depend on the source but will be Dublin Core in most cases. When documents are collected from interviewees or created from images, metadata will be created manually and will be the same as the mandatory items in Dublin Core.

¹ Project funded by ISITE-FUTURE (Université Paris-Est), dedicated to the investigation of citations of retracted papers.

1.5. Digital ephemera

Digital ephemera include various types of data available online on the Internet, collected manually, via dedicated APIs or scrapped with specific codes.

- Tweets

Tweets, posts on X, BlueSky or Mastodon, including textual content, user and publication date) are more and more difficult to retrieve. Tools like DMI-TCAT (that IRIT can make accessible to the project) will be used.

- Comments

We are particularly interested in comments posted on PubPeer, whose owners already agreed to collaborate and provide data. The PubPeer posts produced by NanoBubbles will be posted with a 'Nanobubbles' account. Posts will link to the project's website.

- Annotations

It is part of the project to see how annotations of scientific outputs could benefit the correction of science. The way this kind of data has to be collected and promoted has to be discussed.

- Websites/blogs pages

This includes corporate websites, websites of lab groups in universities or government agencies, conference programs and reports, including CV/resumes or LinkedIn profiles. Apart from manual copies, when possible, the pages will be scraped, but within the conditions of the site and in compliance with the law in force (in any case these data will not be redistributed). We will take snapshots of the webpages of interest using the Internet Archive Wayback Machine (<https://archive.org/web/>) so that future readers can consult the archived pages even if they are no longer online.

- Promotional videos

They will be collected from websites, and might be transcribed if needed.

- Mails from mailing lists

Those mails are textual data which can be retrieved from one's own mailing tool but more conveniently from online archives of listservs.

Except for videos (which might not be numerous), this data results in textual documents in JSON, CSV, TXT or XML format.

The project needs to move forward before we are able to assess the volume this represents as it depends on the delineation of the corpus.

1.6. Software codes

Software and codes will be used according to their licence and will be produced by computer scientists in order to retrieve data and to analyse it. A *private* gitlab repository hosted at the University of Grenoble-Alpes will store the latest version of the code and the entire version history. The code intended for public release will be made available from a *public* gitlab

repository (<https://gricad-gitlab.univ-grenoble-alpes.fr>) hosted at the University of Grenoble-Alpes.

1.7. Experimental data and protocols

Since replication projects will be carried out, this will involve writing the detailed experimental protocols and recording the experiments. Experimental data will originate from measurements performed in a laboratory environment, including images from microscopy experiments, graphs and table from chemical and biochemical analysis, etc

1.8. Physical objects

These objects are given by interviewees or souvenirs/goodies from conferences. If needed, they will be described with dedicated metadata in a readme file.

2. Documentation and data quality

2.1. Recordings and transcripts of interviews

Metadata describing a set of interviews will be stored in a separate readme file, mentioning the place where raw data is stored.

2.2. Field notes

Metadata describing a set of interviews will be stored in a separate readme file, mentioning the place where raw data is stored.

2.3. Scientific literature

The metadata format depends on the database providing them but they will all result in textual files (CSV, JSON...) when it comes to mix different sources before storage and processing. The describing items of the metadata will be based on common standards like Dublin Core or RIS: authors, dates, title, source title, author affiliation, abstract, keywords, DOI, ORCID, number of citations, bibliometric indicators related to the source, ISSN/ISBN, Open Access status. If enrichments come from the project and feed the metadata template, they will be described in a readme file.

The two research engineers will check the consistency of the subsets of metadata.

2.4. Scholarly works metadata

We will not generate metadata for this type of data, but we will nevertheless add a readme file with a short description of the set of metadata contained in a specific folder.

The two research engineers will check the consistency of the subsets of metadata.

2.5. Digital ephemera

The metadata will differ according to the provider of the data and the way we will retrieve data; we will have to decide what template we will use when it comes to providing metadata from scratch.

- **Tweets** come along with a tweetID and a userID, and information about when it has been tweeted, and how many times it has been retweeted or liked. A documentation is available for developers using the API service.
- **Comments** from PubPeer will come along with commentID and userID on Pubpeer, DOI/PubMed ID of the commented paper and its retracted or correction notice if it exists, dates of publication on the platform.
- For **Annotations, Websites/blogs pages, Promotional videos** and **Mails from mailing lists**, the team members will decide in the following months what should be precisely described with the intention to be mixed with other metadata and what should be described as a subset with a simple readme file.

The two research engineers will check the consistency of the subsets of metadata.

2.6. Software codes

Codes will be documented and commented when shared. Digital notebooks will help.

2.7. Experimental data and protocols

The replication project is multisite in the sense that synthesis, characterisation and imaging/sensing will be repeated not just in Levy's lab, but also with partners (collaborators or sub-contractors). In Levy's lab, an open lab notebook and open data approach will be followed, documenting the research process in as much detail as possible and sharing all the data acquired. The partners will be encouraged to follow the same approach and will otherwise be requested to provide a minimum mutually agreed list of data defined at the beginning of the partnership. In that third step, the data are therefore composed of the open lab notebook, the experimental data both internal and from partners, and the communications with the partners.

Replication projects do not start at the beginning of the NanoBubbles project, therefore, decisions about which electronic lab notebook tool to use and how to open the protocols will be discussed soon. The DMP will be updated accordingly in the next version.

2.8. Physical objects

On the occasion of interviews and conferences, the project members collect or receive physical objects of a very varied nature, whether they are goodies or an unexpected object characterising the topic of the interview. These objects are kept by each member but if they become research objects that can be cited, they will be photographed. This image file will then be described with some simple metadata and indexed in the Zotero shared library.

3. Storage and backup during the research process

3.1. Storage spaces

There will be 3 different storage spaces: members' computers, cloud-based storage systems provided by the IT services at all the team members' institutions (data protection guarantee), and SURFdrive, the Dutch secure community cloud system where non-Dutch members will access thanks to guest accounts validated by the University of Maastricht.

The project folder will be our master copy location.

All members get a virtual drive with 500 GB of storage space. Therefore, all non-sensitive data needed to be shared between team members will be stored in the project folder on SURFdrive. Sensitive data will be stored on personal folders on SURFdrive and will not be shared with all team members. The interviewer will give permissions to read those files to selected members. Therefore, thanks to SURFdrive, folders that contain privacy sensitive information will be encrypted and access restricted. Backup and recovery of 30 days are guaranteed.

When it comes to interviews and field notes, data will first be stored on the password protected computer of the interviewer, then synchronized with his/her own encrypted cloud-based storage system (set by his/her institution). USB flash drives are banned. When needed and once anonymized, the files will be shared via SURFdrive.

Computer scientists and research engineers dealing with large files will download and compute them directly on servers at their institutions.

3.2. File-naming convention

We will apply a standardized file-naming convention. Our file names consist of the following items separated by an underscore:

- an abbreviation for the data type,
- a content description (generic to specific),
- the date of modification (international standard: YYYYMMDD),
- a version number (v0.0).

We do not use special characters, full stops or spaces.

Example: WORKS_ScopusExportSNA_20221023_v5.0.csv

Example: EPHEM_Tweets_20221023_v3.6.json

Example: INTERV_ACSCConf_20221023_v1.docx

The abbreviations for data types are:

- INTERV for Recordings and transcripts of interviews
- NOTES for Field notes
- WORKS for Scientific literature
- METADATA for Scholarly works metadata
- EPHEM for Digital ephemera
- CODES for Software codes
- OBJ for Physical objects

4. Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

4.1. Recordings and transcripts of interviews

The interviewer will gain informed consent (see Annex for consent form) from the interviewee for preservation of the data resulting from the interview. In order to comply with the European motto "as open as possible, as closed as necessary", the interviewers will pseudonymise data before sharing.

The pseudonymisation method will be described in a readme file accessible to those researchers who need to access it.

Audio files and raw transcripts will not be uploaded to the common NanoBubbles folder on SURFDrive but will be saved on a dedicated folder with permissions to the interviewer/creator and a minimum number of people who need to see.

4.2. Field notes

When field notes contain personal data, the observer will gain informed consent (see Annex for consent form) from the person observed for preservation of the data resulting from the observation. In order to comply with the European motto "as open as possible, as closed as necessary", the interviewers will pseudonymise data before sharing.

The pseudonymisation method will be described in a readme file.

Field notes with personal data will not be uploaded to the common NanoBubbles folder on SURFDrive but will be saved on a dedicated folder with permissions to the interviewer/creator and the people he has to work with.

4.3. Scientific literature

Intellectual property rights and ownership will of course be respected, although there is no risk of infringing them as the aim of the project is not at all to disseminate the corpus of collected documents, but to analyse them. This is permitted by the European "digital single market" directive of 2019, when text and data mining is for research purposes.

The outputs of the mining process will be data that would be shared.

4.4. Scholarly works metadata

Intellectual property rights and ownership will of course be respected, although there is no risk of infringing them as the aim of the project is not at all to disseminate the corpus of collected documents, but to analyse them. This is permitted by the European "digital single market" directive of 2019, when text and data mining is for research purposes.

The outputs of the mining process will be data that would be shared.

4.5. Digital ephemera

This kind of data is associated with personal data and we are in the process of checking with legal departments how GDPR applies to this.

4.6. Software codes

If existing codes or parts of codes are reused, we will of course respect the licenses associated with the original code.

4.7. Experimental data and protocols

When we have to use protocols already published by others, we will of course cite them.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

We will abide by the European motto "as open as possible, as closed as necessary". Therefore, we will make every effort to share the data we have as soon as possible in compliance with applicable laws.

We will disseminate data as the project progresses, we will not wait until the end of the 5 years to do so.

Data (including codes) will be shared on trusted data repositories like Zenodo or Mendeley data and institutional repositories (e.g.: DataverseNL or the future French data repository) to guarantee longevity, the compliance to the FAIR principles and the possibility to reuse and cite the datasets thanks to the DOI minted by the repositories we will choose.

Standard formats are privileged during the project so no specific tools would be needed to read the data.

For some important outputs, data papers will be published to describe how data were obtained and how to get the most of it.

6. Data management responsibilities and resources

The institutions as members of the consortium will all be responsible for the data. Each interviewer/observer will be in charge of the data files resulting from interviews and field observations. In addition, each interviewer/observer is responsible for adhering to their institution's guidelines. For this reason, two PhD candidates from Radboud University (Wyske Hepkema and Stefan Gaillard) elaborated on this DMP in their DMP for the interview data they are gathering; a PhD student from Maastricht University (Candida Sanchez Burmester) also produced a DMP with the help of the data steward at her faculty. These elaborations entail specifics about with whom their data will be shared; in which locations the data will be saved during the project and archived afterwards; and how they relate to the FAIR principles.

Apart from this type of data, several persons will be in charge of data collection, metadata production, data quality, storage and backup, data archiving, and data sharing:

- Frédérique Bordignon (researcher, bibliometrician),

- Zoé Touré (project manager),
 - 1 research engineer (with skills in data management) placed close to Cyril Labbé (PI).
- Maria Vivas-Romero from University of Maastricht will help as a data steward. WP5 hosts an IT platform whose participants will be partly dedicated to the curation and sharing of the data, and will support other team members when it comes to the technical part.

7. Annex: consent forms

Annex 1

Information Sheet

for oral history interview participants in the research study:

“Nano Bubbles: How, When, and Why Does Science (Fail to) Correct Itself?”

Project overview:

Science relies on the correction of errors to advance, yet in practice scientists find it difficult to remove erroneous and exaggerated claims from the scientific record. The scientific reward system does little to encourage attempts to correct missteps. Nanobubbles is a European Research Council-funded project that combines approaches from the natural, engineering, and social sciences and the humanities to understand how error correction in science works and what obstacles it faces.

The ‘name and shame’ approach that simply target an individual brings many problems, so we are keen to find ways to shift focus back to the role that scientific institutions play in error correction. To achieve this, we are eager to learn about individuals’ experiences with recognizing, testing, debating, and communicating about scientific claims and counter-claims. We hope to foster healthier institutions that incentivize error correction and open debate. We would therefore welcome your participation in this project, and we welcome any questions you may have once you have read the rest of this information sheet.

Inclusion in and withdrawal from the study: If you decide to participate in this project, we will invite you to an interview; see below for details. Interviews are a robust method in the humanities and social sciences for understanding how people construct common practices and understandings. In this study we are interested in how scientific communities do or don’t correct the record. We would like to include you in the study because you participate in a community where correcting the record is an ongoing practice, but your participation is voluntary.

You are free to decline to participate in this study; we will not ask your reasons for doing so, and non-participation carries *no* risks to you. You are also free to withdraw your participation at any time during our interaction or at a later date (see below).

Data storage/use and confidentiality: During your interview we will take written notes and, with your permission we will also make an audio recording. Any notes and recordings associated with your participation in this study will be digitized, and a transcript will be made of your recording. The raw recording and transcript will be kept solely on a secure server that can only be accessed by the project researcher listed at the end of consent form (and their supervisor if they are a PhD

candidate). The project researcher will make a pseudonymized version of the transcript with all identifying information removed. The key associating your pseudonym with your real name will be kept securely and will only be accessible to the project researcher (and supervisor). The pseudonymized transcript (from which identifying information has been removed) will be available to the other project members.

Use of interview/withdrawal from study: You are free to withdraw from the study or alter conditions of participation at any time with no consequences. You will find an identification number at the top of this sheet; if you wish to withdraw from the study or alter conditions of participation, contact the project researcher listed at the end of the consent form as well as Nanobubbles@univ-paris13.fr. Include your identification number in the subject line of your email. That will ensure that the project researcher removes the raw recording and transcript from the secure server. It will also ensure that all members of the project are aware that the pseudonymized transcript is no longer available for use (if that is your wish).

Research materials associated with the project will be stored for ten years after the end of the project. However, no research materials that could be used to identify you will be accessible to anyone outside the project. If we refer to transcripts from our interview with you in a publication, we will contact you to see how you would like us to do so: we can either attribute the reference to you by your real name, or we can use a pseudonym and modify any details that could be used to identify you. Both attribution by name and pseudonymization/de-identification are standard practice in historical research; we leave the choice to you.

If you withdraw your participation before any publications that refer to your interview have been published, we will withdraw both your pseudonymized and raw data from our server. However, if a publication referring to your interview has already been published when you notify us of your wish to withdraw, then we can only remove the portion of the interview transcript that has not yet been referred to in a publication. We will, in any case, follow your instructions not to refer to your interview in future publications.

Length: We plan for interviews for this project to last between one and two hours maximum. The median interview will be approximately 80 minutes, so we would ask you to block out between 90 minutes to 2 hours to meet with us; if you are only available for a smaller amount of time we are grateful for whatever time you can spare for us. You are free to end the interview at any time. You are also welcome to ask for additional time, though we commit to not going past the two hours without this explicit request. If necessary, we may be willing to talk with you more than once to accommodate your willingness to share information with us, though this will of course depend on our availability and yours.

Format: We use a semi-structured interview format; we do not have a list of questions that we strictly adhere to, but instead we have a set of topics to cover at some point in the interview. We will pose questions related to topics as they naturally come up in our conversation. The topics may relate to themes such as: when do scientists feel they should scrutinize a claim; how do they do so; how do they react to others' attempts to scrutinize or correct claims; how do they react to scrutiny that is applied to their own claims; how do they adjudicate claims and counter-claims; what is their experience with mechanisms for correcting the scientific record; how do they find, encounter, and interpret corrections to the record; etc. The questions may alternatively (or additionally) relate to the histories of specific fields that have seen rapid (bubble-like) growth, such as biotechnology and nanotechnology: what was your participation in those fields; what was the role of conferences and journals in the growth of those fields; what counted as exciting claims in those fields. The semi-structured interview format allows you to guide the conversation to a significant degree. If there are topics that you feel we ought to spend more time on (or other

topics that we haven't asked about), then we want you to move the conversation in that direction.

Recording: We prefer to record the conversation so that we can transcribe it. This makes it easier to refer to the conversation later and to share the pseudonymized interview transcript with members of the project. However, you may *at any time* request that we stop (or start) the recorder. The recording and raw transcript will be kept on a secure server where it can only be accessed by the project researcher identified at the end of the consent form (and their supervisor if they are a PhD candidate).

Interview materials: During the interview we may ask if you have any documents related to the topics we've discussed that you would like to share with us. If you do, then we will make a copy and return the original to you; an electronic version of the copy will be stored in the same secure folder as the interview recording, raw transcript, and notes; this folder can only be accessed by the project research identified at the end of the consent form (and their supervisor if they are a PhD candidate). Altogether the contents of that folder constitute the interview materials relating to our conversation. Dutch law requires us to retain the interview materials for ten years after the end of the project (i.e., until 2036). You may specify now what you would like us to do with those interview materials at that time if we are unable to contact you. We will make every attempt to contact you, and if successful then your instructions at that point supersede any instructions you give us now. You may also contact the project researcher at any time to withdraw your interview materials from use in the study's future publications; as noted above, materials referenced in past or accepted publications cannot be removed. Withdrawing from the study will carry *no* penalties or risks for you.

Results of study: The Nanobubbles project will result in a number of publications in peer-reviewed journals, edited volume chapters, monographs, etc. All publications will be Open Access and available at the project website. As noted above, we will contact you before referring to your interview in a publication; we will also send you a copy of that publication once it appears.

Annex 2

Declaration of Consent

for participation in the research study:

"Nano Bubbles: How, When, and Why Does Science (Fail to) Correct Itself?"

I confirm that I have received and read the information sheet describing this study, my rights as a participant in the study, and the project researchers' responsibilities to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the study. I have been able to think about my participation in the study and any conditions on that participation that I would like the project researchers to adhere to. My participation is voluntary. I have the right to withdraw my consent or modify my conditions for participating at any time before, during, or after my participation in the study. This includes ending an interview or other interaction with project researchers at any time and/or refusing to allow references to my participation to appear in future project publications. I may contact Nanobubbles@univ-paris13.fr (using the code provided with this information sheet) at any time with further questions, to withdraw my participation, or to request changes to the conditions of my participation. I may contact the project researcher's

institution's Data Protection Officer if I have questions about my data or about my interactions with the project researcher.

I agree to participate in the study.

Additional Conditions

I agree that my interview will be recorded and transcribed.

- o The recording and raw transcript will be kept on a secure server and only accessible to the project researcher (and supervisor if applicable). A pseudonymized transcript with identifying information removed will be accessible to other project members. Portions of the raw transcript may only be made available to others with my permission. Even if you agree to recording of the interview, you may ask for the recorder to be turned off at any time.

I understand that the transcript, recording, notes, and any accompanying materials will be retained for ten years after the end of the project (i.e., until 2036) unless I request their removal before then. However, only the unpublished portions of the transcripts can be removed once publications that refer to them have appeared. After 2036 I would like the project researcher to:

- ___ destroy the interview materials
- ___ retain them securely in their own possession, pursuant to other conditions agreed to on this form
- ___ contact me for further instructions
- ___ other: _____

My participation in the study is further conditional upon the following:

Name of study participant:

Signature:

Date:

The undersigned, responsible researcher, declares that the said person has been informed orally and in writing about the study mentioned above.

Name:

Institution:

Function:

Email address:

Signature:

Date:

Annex 3

Information Sheet

for ethnographic interview participants in the research study:

"Nano Bubbles: How, When, and Why Does Science (Fail to) Correct Itself?"

Project overview:

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The 'name and shame' approach that simply target an individual brings many problems, so we are keen to find ways to shift focus back to the role that scientific institutions play in error correction. To achieve this, we are eager to learn about individuals' experiences with recognizing, testing, debating, and communicating about scientific claims and counter-claims. We hope to foster healthier institutions that incentivize error correction and open debate. We would therefore welcome your participation in this project, and we welcome any questions you may have once you have read the rest of this information sheet.

Inclusion in and withdrawal from the study: If you decide to participate in this project, we will invite you to an interview; see below for details. Interviews are a robust method in the humanities and social sciences for understanding how people construct common practices and understandings. In this study we are interested in how scientific communities do or don't correct the record. We would like to include you in the study because you participate in a community where correcting the record is an ongoing practice, but your participation is voluntary.

You are free to decline to participate in this study; we will not ask your reasons for doing so, and non-participation carries *no* risks to you. You are also free to withdraw your participation at any time during our interaction or at a later date (more details below).

Data storage/use and confidentiality: During your interview we will take written notes and, with your permission we will also make an audio recording. Any notes and recordings associated with your participation in this study will be digitized, and a transcript will be made of your recording. The raw data, including the recording and transcript, will be kept solely on the password-protected, secure Surfdrive server. The raw data can only be accessed by the project researcher (and their supervisor if they are a PhD candidate). The project researcher will make a pseudonymized version of the transcript with all identifying information removed. The key associating your pseudonym with your real name will also be kept on the secure server and will only be accessible to the project researcher (and supervisor). The pseudonymized transcript (from which identifying information has been removed) will only be available to other project members whose projects specifically require them to work that data.

Withdrawal from study: You are free to withdraw from the study or alter conditions of participation at any time with no consequences. You will find an identification number at the top of this sheet; if you wish to withdraw from the study or alter conditions of participation, contact the project researcher listed at the end of the consent form as well as Nanobubbles@univ-paris13.fr. Include your identification number in the subject line of your email. That will ensure that the project researcher removes the raw recording and transcript from the secure server. It will also ensure that all members of the project are aware that the pseudonymized transcript is no longer available for use (if that is your wish).

As required by Dutch law, research materials associated with the project will be stored for ten years after the end of the project. However, no research materials that could be used to identify you will be accessible to anyone outside the project. If we refer to transcripts from our interview with you in a presentation or publication, we will modify any details that could be used to identify you; this is a standard practice in the social sciences. If you withdraw your participation before any publications that refer to your pseudonymized data have been published, we will withdraw both your pseudonymized and raw data from our server. However, if a publication referring to your pseudonymized data has already been published when you notify us of your wish to withdraw, then we can only remove the raw data but not the pseudonymized transcript. We will, in any case, follow your instructions not to refer to your pseudonymized data in future publications.

Length: We plan for interviews for this project to last between one and two hours maximum. The median interview will be approximately 80 minutes, so we would ask you to block out between 90 minutes to 2 hours to meet with us; if you are only available for a smaller amount of time we are grateful for whatever time you can spare for us. You are free to end the interview at any time. You are also welcome to ask for additional time, though we commit to not going past the two hours without this explicit request. If necessary, we may be willing to talk with you more than once to accommodate your willingness to share information with us, though this will of course depend on our availability and yours.

Format: We use a semi-structured interview format; we do not have a list of questions that we strictly adhere to, but instead we have a set of topics to cover at some point in the interview. We will pose questions related to topics as they naturally come up in our conversation. The topics relate to these broad themes: when do scientists feel they should scrutinize a claim; how do they do so; how do they react to others' attempts to scrutinize or correct claims; how do they react to scrutiny that is applied to their own claims; how do they adjudicate claims and counter-claims; what is their experience with mechanisms for correcting the scientific record; how do they find, encounter, and interpret corrections to the record; etc. This format allows you to guide the conversation to a significant degree. If there are topics that you feel we ought to spend more time on (or other topics that we haven't asked about), then we want you to move the conversation in that direction.

Recording: We prefer to record the conversation so that we can transcribe it. This makes it easier to refer to the conversation later and to share the pseudonymized interview transcript with members of the project. However, you may *at any time* request that we stop (or start) the recorder. The recording and raw transcript will be kept on a secure server where it can only be accessed by the project researcher identified at the top of this form (and their supervisor if they are a PhD candidate).

Interview materials: During the interview we may ask if you have any documents related to the topics we've discussed that you would like to share with us. If you do, then we will make a copy and return the original to you; an electronic version of the copy will be stored in the same secure folder as the interview recording, raw transcript, and notes; this folder can only be accessed by the project research identified at the end of the consent form (and their supervisor if they are a PhD candidate). Altogether the contents of that folder constitute the interview materials relating to our conversation. Dutch law requires us to retain the interview materials for ten years after the end of the project (i.e., until 2036). At that point the data will be destroyed unless we are able to contact you and you grant permission to preserve it for a given amount of time. You may also contact the project researcher at *any time* to withdraw your interview materials from use in the study's future publications; as noted above, materials referenced in past or accepted publications cannot be removed. Withdrawing from the study will carry *no* penalties or risks for you.

Results of study: The Nanobubbles project will result in a number of publications in peer-reviewed journals, edited volume chapters, monographs, etc. All publications will be Open Access and available at the project website.

Post-publication clarification: The Nanobubbles project is committed to the practice of post-publication review. Accordingly, we will make all our publications available for public review and clarification. When we send you a copy of any publication that cites your interview, we will indicate where you can annotate that publication with your comments or clarifications. You will be able to do so both anonymous and/or by name – the choice will be yours.

Data Protection Officer: The Data Protection Officer (DPO) at the project researcher's institution is identified at the top of this information sheet. If you have questions about your data, your interactions with the project researcher, and/or your interactions with any other member of the Nanobubbles team, please contact the DPO. The DPO is not affiliated with the Nanobubbles project in any way, and therefore acts entirely independently of the project. You may discuss your data and/or your treatment by project staff with the DPO with *no* consequences for yourself.